

AGROCHEMICAL USAGE IN NIGERIA: PROFILE AND COST

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ABSTRACT

Data were obtained in February, 2022 from the Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Abuja on fertilizers use in Nigeria from 2010 to 2020. These data include fertilizer types, total cost of fertilizers, and net cost by types within the periods. Also annual cost by types of fertilizers, percentages by types were analyzed. Similarly, data were obtained from NBS on pesticides expenditure in Nigeria in the same period. The pesticide types are herbicides, insecticides, fungicides, soil fumigants (methyl bromide) and mosquito repellent coils. The total pesticide use costs, pesticide type costs and the mean annual cost for the period were evaluated. The monetary values in Naira and US Dollars were determined considering the exchange rates at each specific period to ascertain the real national expenditure on fertilizers and pesticide usage. Based on fertilizer types, 82 % were nitrogenous and multiple-element fertilizers with each having a share of 41% apiece, while the potassic fertilizers had 11 %, phosphoric 5 % and others 2 %. Among the others were animal and vegetable fertilizers either in single or mixed form and fertilizer products that were not properly identified. A sum of 44.7 billion Naira (\$209.14 million) was established to be spent annually on fertilizers in Nigeria. In the same vein, about 63.4 billion Naira was also spent annually on pesticides, (\$244 million) out of which 74%, 16.6%, 4.7%, 5.0% and 0.06% went to herbicides, insecticides, fungicides, soil fumigants, and mosquito repellent coils respectively. In total, Nigeria spent about 108.1 billion Naira (\$453.14) on agro-chemicals annually of which 59% and 41% were on pesticides and fertilizers respectively.

Keywords: Agrochemicals, Costs, Fertilizers, Pesticides, Profile.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria has a total geographical area of 923 768 square kilometers which lies wholly within the tropics along the Gulf of Guinea extending from Latitude 04. 03⁰ N to 14.00⁰ N and Longitude 02.05^o E to nearly 15.00^o E. It has a total land area of 92.4 million hectares of which 70.8 million hectares have potential for agricultural production while 34 million hectares are arable (World Bank, 2020). The agroecology is highly stratified due to differential rainfall distribution patterns, which favors the production of a wide range of agricultural products, therefore, making agriculture one of the most important sectors of the economy. The agricultural sector is the major source of employment generation and contribution to gross domestic product (GDP) and export revenue earnings after petroleum. However, despite rich agricultural potential, the sector has been growing at a slow rate (Manyong *et al.*, 2005). Less than 50 % of the country's arable land is under cultivation because the larger proportion of the farmers are smallholder and traditional farmers who use rudimentary production techniques, with resultant low yields (Manyong *et al.*, 2005). These smallholder farmers are constrained by myriads of problems including poor access to modern inputs and credit, poor infrastructure, inadequate access to markets, land and

environmental degradation. The poor access to modern inputs and inadequate agrochemicals such as fertilizers and pesticides coupled with the marginal nature of soils are limiting factors to agricultural expansion. For this study, the agrochemicals are fertilizers and pesticides.

In a global checklist of data on pesticide use among 193 countries published by FAOSTAT (2019) and World Bank (2019), Nigeria was conspicuously not listed because of the dearth of such statistics. There is similar dearth of published information on fertilizers usages and costs in Nigeria, therefore, the essence of this study was to unfold the cost of fertilizers and pesticides use in Nigeria from 2010 to 2020 with a view to making an empirical analysis with respect to the followings: (i) to unfold the types of fertilizers and pesticides in the country, (ii) to determine the total cost of fertilizers and pesticides used within the periods, (iii) to determine the annual cost of fertilizers and pesticides usage in Nigeria, (iv) to determine the cost by types of fertilizers and pesticides and (iv) to determine which among these agrochemicals Nigeria expended more resources.

Fertilizers

Fertilizer is any substance that is added to the soil to supply those elements required in nutrition of plants. Plant nutrients are those elements that are required by plant for its growth and synthesis of cellular components. These elements can be grouped primary elements (C, O, H, N, P and K) and secondary elements (B, Cu, Fe, Zn, Mn, Mo, Cl and Ni). Among the elements listed above, Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium are the most important in plant nutrition. These elements form the basis for formulations of inorganic fertilizers (Adepetu *et al.*, 2014). Inorganic fertilizers contain one or several plant nutrients that are mostly present in concentrated and easily soluble forms. The value of a given inorganic fertilizer depends on the contents of its pure nutrients.

In Nigeria, the focus is on these primary elements, NPK, with the assumption that what most crops need is in the order of $N > P > K$ (not $N = P = K$). While this is so in theory, in practice and with the intervention of different environmental impacts and variability, the assumption needs to be modified to suit the actual parameters on the ground.

Fertilizers can be classified in several ways, but the most practical methods are based on origin, type of formulations, bulk blending, granulation, fluid, mixed, nutrient composition, single element or straight, incomplete, complete and compound fertilizers (Adepetu *et al.*, 2014)). Based on origin fertilizers could be inorganic or organic. Organic fertilizer is a by-product from the processing of animal or vegetable substances that contain sufficient plant nutrients to be of value as fertilizers, while inorganic fertilizer is any material of natural or synthetic origin added to soil to supply certain elements essential to the growth of plants.

Brady and Weil (1999) also classified fertilizers on the basis of formulations as solid fertilizer materials blended together in small blending plants and delivered to the farm in bulk. These are fertilizers that are present in the form of stable granules of uniform size, which facilitate ease of handling the materials and reduce undesirable dusts. Fluid fertilizers contain essential elements in liquid forms, either as soluble nutrients or as liquid suspensions or both. Mixed fertilizers contains two or more fertilizer minerals mixed together as dry powders, granules, pellets, bulk blends or liquids. Based on nutrient composition fertilizers can be classified as single or straight fertilizers and incomplete fertilizers and complete fertilizers. These fertilizers contain only one fertilizer

element, examples are: Ammonium Sulphate 21 % N, Urea 46 % N and Muriate of potash 60 % K₂O. Incomplete fertilizers contain two fertilizer elements such as Nitrogen and Phosphorus or Nitrogen and Potassium. Examples include; NPK 26-12-0, Ammophos 16-20-0 and Di-ammonium phosphate 18-46-0. In complete fertilizers all the three most important plant nutrients, N, P and K are present, examples are NPK 15-15-15 and NPK 20-10-10. Incomplete and complete fertilizers are known as compound fertilizers. While incomplete compound fertilizers contain any two of the nutrients, N, P and K.

Pesticide

A pesticide is any substance or mixture of substances used to prevent development of, repel, destroy or kill a pest. The term pesticide refers to insecticides, herbicides, fungicides and various other substances used to control pests. Some pesticides are classified as restricted use pesticides if there is reason to believe they could harm humans, livestock, wildlife, or the environment, even when used according to label directions. To apply these types of pesticides, a person is required to have pesticide applicator certification or be under the direct supervision of a certified applicator.

All other pesticides are classified as unclassified/general-use pesticides. These can be applied by anyone according to label directions. Many household pesticides are under this category. They are cockroach sprays and baits, insect repellents to repel mosquitoes and other biting insects, rat and other rodent poisons, flea and tick sprays, powders and pet collars, kitchen, laundry and bath disinfectants and sanitisers, products that kill moulds and mildew, lawn and garden products such as herbicide and swimming pool chemicals.

Pesticides are made up of one or more active ingredients (AI) and inert ingredients. The AI is the material that controls the pests. The inert ingredients are used to dilute the active ingredients and or are substances to help active ingredients target the pest.

Many types of pesticides are available to control pests. Pesticides are classified based on pests they control, herbicides control weeds and other unwanted vegetation, and fungicides destroy fungi that infect plants, animals and people. Insecticides control insects that infest plants, animals or people while nematicides control nematodes etc.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data were obtained in February, 2021 from the Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) on fertilizers and pesticides imports into Nigeria from 2010 to 2020. These data include fertilizer types, total cost of fertilizers, and net cost by types within the periods. Also annual cost by types of fertilizers, percentages by types were analyzed.

The pesticide types were herbicides, insecticides, fungicides, soil fumigants (methyl bromide) and mosquito repellent coils. The total pesticide use costs, pesticide type costs and the mean annual cost for the periods were evaluated. The monetary values in Naira and US Dollars were determined considering the exchange rates at each specific period in order to ascertain the actual national expenditure on fertilizers and pesticide usage.

RESULTS

Fertilizers Profile and Costs

The fertilizer profile in Table 1 indicated the various components of fertilizers and their cost implications, while Table 2 further classified the fertilizers into nitrogenous, phosphoric, multiple-element fertilizers, potassic, and other fertilizers respectively. As indicated in Table 2, a sum of 44.7 billion Naira (\$ 209.14 million) was spent annually on fertilizers. When the fertilizer costs were de-aggregated into types, 18.3 billion, 2.4 billion, 18.5 billion, 5.0 billion and 634 million Naira went to nitrogenous, phosphoric, multiple-elements fertilizers, potassic, and other fertilizers respectively. Based on fertilizer types, 82 % of the expenditure went to nitrogenous and multiple-element fertilizers with each having a share of 41% apiece, while the potassium fertilizer had 11 %, phosphorus 5 % and others with 2 % of total cost respectively as depicted in Fig. 1. Among the other fertilizer types were animal and vegetable fertilizers either in single or mixed and fertilizer products that were not properly identified.

Table 1: Cost implications of fertilizer usage in Nigeria from 2010-2020.

FERTILIZERS Descriptions	Total Value (Naira)	Mean Value (Naira)
	2010-2020	2010-2020
Animal or vegetable fertilizers, whether or not mixed together.	3 748 936 109.00	340 812 373.55
Urea, whether or not in aqueous solution	84 368 830 659.00	7 669 893 696.27
Ammonium sulphate	14 053 522 099.00	1 277 592 918.09
Other double salts, mixtures of ammonium sulphate and ammonium nitrate	984 057 553.00	89 459 777.55
Ammonium nitrate, whether or not in aqueous solution	5 243 021 621.00	476 638 329.18
Sodium nitrate	442 190 665.00	40 199 151.36
Double salts and mixtures of calcium nitrate and ammonium nitrate	86 129 613.00	7 829 964.82
Mixtures of urea and ammonium nitrate in aqueous or ammonial solution	151 930 398.00	13 811 854.36
Other, including mixtures not specified in the foregoing subheadings	3 225 040 793.00	293 185 526.64
Superphosphates	9 110 915 578.00	828 265 052.55
Mineral or chemical fertilizer phosphate, other.	12 471 299 533.00	1 133 754 503.00
Potassium chloride	38 655 234 531.00	3 514 112 230.09
Potassium sulphate	9 819 436 220.00	892 676 020.00
Other Mineral or chemical fertilizers, potassic; Not specified or included	5 733 943 742.00	521 267 612.91
Tablets or similar forms or in P	4 534 876 636.00	412,261,512.36
Mineral or chemical fertilizers containing the three fertilizers	195 242 585 952.00	17 749 325 995.64
Diammonium hydrogenorthophosphate (Diammonium phosphate)	50 652 384 795.00	4 604 762 254.09
Ammonium dihydrogenorthophosphate (Monoammonium phosphate)	1 748 379 656.00	158 943 605.09
Containing nitrates and phosphates	43 301 159 350.00	3 936 469 031.82
Mineral or chemical fertilizers containing other	7 171 186 467.00	651 926 041.46
Mineral or chemical fertilizers containing the two fertilizers	1 131 490 845.00	102 862 804.09
Total Cost (Naira (#)	491 876 552 815.00	44 716 050 255.91
Total Cost (\$)	2 300 571 918.85	209 142 901.71

Source: Computed with data extracted from NBS (2022)

Table 2: Annual cost implications of fertilizer use by types in Nigeria from 2010-2020 in Naira

(#)	Total Value (#)	Mean Value (#)
FERTILIZERS		
Nitrogenous Fertilizers	2010-2020	2010-2020
Urea, whether or not in aqueous solution	84 368 830 659.00	7 669 893 696.27
Ammonium sulphate	14 053 522 099.00	1 277 592,918.09
Other double salts, mixtures of ammonium sulphate and ammonium nitrate	984 057 553.00	89 459 777.55
Ammonium nitrate, whether or not in aqueous solution	5 243 021 621.00	476 638 329.18
Sodium nitrate	442 190 665.00	40 199 151.36
Double salts and mixtures of calcium nitrate and ammonium nitrate	86 129 613.00	7 829 964.82
Mixtures of urea and ammonium nitrate in aqueous or ammonial solution	151 930 398.00	13 811 854.36
Diammonium hydrogenorthophosphate (Diammonium phosphate	50 652 384 795.00	4 604 762 254.09
Ammonium dihydrogenorthophosphate (Monoammonium phosphate	1 748 379 656.00	158 943 605.09
Containing nitrates and phosphates	43 301 159 350.00	3 936 469 031.82
Sub total	201 031 606 409.00	18 275 600 582.63
Phosphorous fertilizers		
Super phosphate	9 110 915 578.00	828 265 052.55
Mineral or chemical fertilizer phosphate	12 471 299 533.00	1 133 754 503.00
Tablets or similar forms or in P	4 534 876 636.00	412 261 512.36
Sub total	26 117 091 747.00	2 374 281 067.91
Potassium fertilizers		
Potassium chloride	38 655 234 531.00	3,514,112,230.09
Potassium sulphate	9 819 436 220.00	892 676 020.00
Other minerals or chemical fertilizers, potassic	5 733 943 742.00	521 267 612.91
Sub total	54 208 614 493.00	4 928 055 863.00
Multiple-element fertilizers		
Mineral or chemical fertilizers containing the three fertilizers	195 242 585 952.00	17 749 325 995.64
Mineral or chemical fertilizers containing the two fertilizers	1 131 490 845.00	102 862 804.09
Mineral or chemical fertilizers containing others	7 171 186 467.00	651 926 041.46
Sub total	203 545 263 264.00	18 504 114 841.19
Others		
Animal or vegetable fertilizers, whether or not mixed together	3 748 936 109.00	340 812 373.55
Other, including mixtures not specified in the above listed	3 225 040 793.00	293 185 526.64
Sub total	6 973 976 902.00	633 997 900.19
Grand total	491 876 552 815.00	44 716 050 254.92

Source: Computed with data extracted from NBS (2022)

Fig 1: Percentage cost by fertilizer types in Nigeria from 2010-2020.

Source (Computed with data extracted from NBS (2022)).

Pesticides Profile and Costs

Similarly, Nigeria spent about 63.4 billion Naira (\$244 million) annually on pesticides, (Tables 3 and 4), out of which 74%, 16.6%, 4.7%, 5.0% and 0.06% of the expenditure went to herbicides, insecticides, fungicides, soil fumigants, and mosquito repellent coils respectively as shown in figure 2.

Table 3- Pesticides use costs (#) in Nigeria from 2010-2020

Year	Herbicides	Insecticides	Fungicides	Soil Fumigants (Methyl bromide)	Mosquito Repellant coils	Total Annual Cost
			(#)			
2010	8 866 193 020	8 571 677 710	1 063 816 607	0.00	29 629 904	18 531 317 241
2011	19 327 625 900	10 716 987 710	1 336 969 510	0.00	8 655 332	31 390 238 452
2012	27 600 862 196	9 170 731 277	2 236 943 746	0.00	15 821	39 008 553 040
2013	25 435 305 955	17 650 800 560	2 154 025 534	0.00	35 232 947	45 275 364 996
2014	53 571 520 971	15 985 623 190	1 592 749 911	0.00	81 064 811	71 230 958 883
2015	42 245 257 505	4 374 936 915	2 744 233 798	217 785 768	5 712 951	49 587 926 937
2016	21 520 707 316	1 653 300 993	2 442 138 315	3 766 799 788	0.00	29 382 946 412
2017	59 529 425 330	1 247 98 564	2 603 457 329	10 918 107 491	9 530 143.39	74 308 501 857
2018	87 720 842 541	1 027 075 299	4 041 526 713	7 122 048 760	365 853	99 911 859 166
2019	76 939 717 569	1 311 094 284	2 864 065 876	6 982 802 199	23 470 599	88 121 150 527
2020	125 569 237 376	3 184 939 162	6 715 306 740	14 909 613 831	29 002 435	150 408 000 000
Total	548 327 000 000	74 895 148 664	29 795 234 079	43 917 157 837	222 680 796	697 157 000 000
Mean Annual Cost	49 847 909 090	6 808 649 879	2 708 657 643	3 992 468 894	20 243 708.73	63 377 909 090

Source: (Computed with data extracted from NBS, 2021 and 2022.

Table 4 -Pesticides use costs (US\$) in Nigeria from 2010-2020

Year	Herbicides	Insecticides	Fungicides	Soil Fumigants	Mosquito Repellant coils	Total Annual Cost (US\$)	#/US\$ Exchange Rates
				(US\$)			
2010	56 907 529	55 017 186.84	6 828 091.19	000	190 179.10	118 942 986.10	#155.8/US\$
2011	125 618 262.70	69 654 151.24	8 689 519.76	000	562 559.03	204 524 492.70	#153.86/US\$
2012	175 243 569.50	58 226 865.25	14 202 817.43	000	100.45	247 673 352.60	#157.50/US\$
2013	161 689 059.50	112 203 932.10	13 692 870.98	000	223 971.44	287 809 834.	#157.31/US\$
2014	337 884 080.50	100 823 861.20	10 045 726.34	000	511 288.62	449 264 956.70	#158.55/US\$
2015	219 524 306.30	22 734 030.94	14 260 204.73	1 131 707.38	29 686.92	257 679 936.20	#192.44/US\$
2016	84 897 657.94	6 522 154.70	9 634 061.76	14 859 756.95	000	115 913 631.30	#253.47/US\$
2017	194 674 205.60	4 081 171.93	8 513 873.34	35 704 592.99	31 165.65	243 005 009.50	#305.79/US\$
2018	286 594 493.40	3 355 577.95	13 204 151.57	23 268 585.85	1 195.29	326 424 004.10	#306.08/US\$
2019	25 080 513.25	4 270 665.42	9 329 204.80	22 745 284.04	76 451.46	61 502 118.97	#307.00/US\$
2020	311 586 196.80	7 903 074.84	16 663 292.16	36 996 560.37	71 966.34	373 221 090.51	#403.00/US\$
Total	1 979 699 874.49	444 792 672.41	125 063 814.06	134 706 487.58	1 698 564.30	2 685 961 412.84	
Mean Annual Cost	179 972 715.8	40 435 697.49	11 369 437.64	12 246 044.32	154 414.94	244 178 310.3	

Source: (Computed with data extracted from NBS,

Fig 2: Percentage cost by pesticide types in Nigeria from 2010-2020.

Source (Computed with data extracted from NBS (2022))

Gross Expenditure on Agrochemicals

On a general note, Nigeria expended about 108.1 billion Naira annually on agro-chemicals out of which 59% and 41% were on pesticides and fertilizers respectively as shown in fig 3.

Fig 3: Percentage costs of agrochemicals in Nigeria from 2010-2020.
Source (Computed with data extracted from NBS (2022))

Discussion

It is obvious that Nigeria expended more resources on the nitrogenous fertilizers and multiple-elements fertilizers (82%) as indicated in figure 1. The higher demand for nitrogenous fertilizers could be ascribed to nitrogen as the most limiting nutrient in Nigerian soils (FPDD, 1989). This is more serious particularly in the savanna agro-ecological zones where the soils are predominantly coarse textured and characteristically low in organic matter (FPDD, 1989). In the forest agro-ecological zones where rainfall is usually heavy, nitrogen is easily lost by leaching and denitrification under water-logged conditions (FPDD, 1989). The fertilizer supply and demand in Nigeria is in congruent with FAO (2019) which reports that the world fertilizer supply and demand trends and outlook shows that the world agricultural needs for fertilizers is $N > P > K$ while the Nigerian fertilizers supply and demand is $N > K > P$ as depicted in tables 1,2 and figure 1.

Explicitly, Nigeria expended about 108.1 billion Naira annually on agro-chemicals out of which 59% and 41% were on pesticides and fertilizers respectively (fig 3). The lower expenditure in fertilizers could be attributed to the fact that very few crops such as rice and maize are considered indispensable for fertilizer application while other crops could be managed without fertilizers.

The high rate of expenditure on pesticides was necessitated by huge number of youths embracing agriculture as a business particularly, crop production (fig 3). These youth applied a lot of pesticides, particularly herbicides in order to avert drudgery in weeding. Crop production in Nigeria is highly rain-fed skewed and the rainfall is so erratic which favors weed infestation. (Usman *et al.*, 2013). Also more significant chunk of pesticides and insecticides are employed in domestic pest control such as weeding of household surroundings, industrial sites and mosquitoes. In the USA, pesticide expenditure accounts for approximately 16-18% of the entire world (Atwood and Paisley-Jones, 2017) and herbicides (59%) accounted for significant portion of the expenditure followed by insecticides (14%) and fungicides (10%) (Atwood and Paisley-Jones, 2017).

CONCLUSION

A sum of 44.7 billion Naira (US\$ 209.14 million) was spent annually on fertilizer in Nigeria. On the basis of fertilizer types, 82 % of the expenditure were on nitrogenous and multiple-element fertilizers with each having a share of 41% apiece, while the potassium fertilizer had 11 %, phosphorus 3 % and others 2 %. Among the others were animal and vegetable fertilizers either in single or mixed form and fertilizer products that were not properly identified. Similarly, about 63.4 billion Naira was also went to herbicides, insecticides, fungicides, soil fumigants, and mosquito repellent coils respectively. In total Nigeria spent about 108.1 billion Naira (US\$ 453.14 million) on agro-chemicals annually.

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